

Impact of Smart Phone Communication Technology and Instagram Social-Media on Student Political Participation Prior to the 2019 Presidential Elections: STKIP Pasundan Cimahi Batch 2018 Students' Research

Jajang Hendar Hendrawan¹, Edy Sofyan², Nana Supriatna³

^{1,2,3}STKIP Pasundan, Cimahi, Indonesia

Email: jajang_hendra@stkippasundan.ac.id

Abstract

Student political participation in the 2014 presidential election sparked this study's development. There were 190.3 million registered voters in this year's presidential election; 57 million of those voted abstentionally, or 24.89 percent of the electorate. This low political participation arises since there is a lot of news and information on the 2019 Presidential Election from profiles on Instagram social media. News that is both factual and false can have a significant impact on how people respond to news in the 2019 Presidential Elections. The problem formulation in this study is as follows: 1) Is there any influence of smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media on STKIP Pasundan students' political participation? 2). How influential are smartphone communication technologies and Instagram social media on STKIP Pasundan students' political participation in 2018? The goal of this study was to see how smartphone communication technologies and Instagram social media affected STKIP Pasundan students' political participation in 2018. This study employs a quantitative approach to data collection. Random sampling is used in this experiment. The findings of this research indicate that 1) There is no influence of smartphone communication tools on the level of political engagement of students from the class of 2018 at STKIP Pasundan, as shown by the findings of t count 0.561 t table 1.664. 2) The results of t count 5.747 and t table 1.664 indicate that there is an influence of social media Instagram on the political engagement of STKIP Pasundan students from the class of 2018. This is due of the first finding. 3) Both independent variables 1 and 2 have an influence on the dependent variable at the same time since the F count for the entire experiment is greater than the F table for the entire experiment. 4) The value of the coefficient of determination is 40.02 percent, and the remaining 59.98 percent is determined by other variables that are outside of the scope of this study.

Keywords: *Smartphone Communication Tool, Instagram Social-Media, Political Participation.*

INTRODUCTION

Elections are one of the democratic ideals upheld by the State of Indonesia, a sovereign nation. A general election is a direct, public, confidential, honest, open, and fair way for the people to exercise their sovereignty over their own destinies and government. When it comes to democratic procedures and instruments, elections are a testament to their ability to actualize and aggregate people's interests. Political participation in a democratic democracy indicates that the highest legitimate state power (people's sovereignty) is being exercised by the people (Putra, Susanti, Yusari, Silitonga, & Amrie, 2014, p. 4). For Miriam Budiardjo in Fenyapwain (2013, pp. 6-7), political involvement is the act of an individual or group actively participating in political life, specifically through electing state leaders and influencing government policies in some way directly or indirectly (public policies). Activities that fall into this category include voting in elections, attending general meetings, becoming a member of a political party or interest organization and so on. Political participation, according to Sudijono Sastroatmodjo in Rahmadani (2017, p. 3), is essential to a democratic state order and is a sign of political modernisation. In a country ruled by a small group of powerful elites, citizens have a minimal impact on how decisions are made and how society as a whole is run. There is a tendency for simple folks to be overlooked in the political arena. Democracy (participation) is based on the belief that the person who understands the most about what is best for themselves is the individual themselves, according to Suryo Sakti Hadiwijo in Rahmadani (2017, p. 5). In order for the government's political decisions to have a direct impact on people's lives, citizens must have a say in the substance and the essence of those decisions. For the sake of completeness, citizen involvement in political decision-making is a need.

Husni Kamil Malik, Chairman of the General Elections Commission (KPU), stated that 190,307,134 voters participated in the 2014 Presidential Election, including 188,268,423 domestic voters and 2,038,711 international voters. They allocated their voting rights at 478,685 domestic polling stations (TPS), 495 abroad polling stations, and 130 Overseas Election Committees (Mulya, 2014). Husni also stated that the percentage of voters in the 2014 Presidential Election was 69.58 percent (Detiknews, 2014) and 75.11 percent (Detiknews, 2014). (Mulya, 2014). Prabowo-Hatta received around 47.12 percent or 60,983,737 votes, while Jokowi-JK received 52.87 percent or 68,434,018 votes. Meanwhile, the Information and Communications Institute (Infokom) Muhammadiyah Malang (2014) stated that Prabowo-Hatta received 58,457,509

votes (47.51 percent) from the incoming data of 89.95 percent or 123,039,121 votes, while Jokowi-JK received 64,581,612 votes (52.49 percent). The greater the amount of political participation, the more individuals observe, comprehend, and participate in state actions. A low level of political participation, on the other hand, often shows a lack of appreciation or interest in state concerns or actions. The attitude of political groups (golput) in elections reflects the low level of people's political participation. It should be mentioned that the implementation of elections in Indonesia has been characterized by the tug-of-war between diverse parties, both political players and the public, from the beginning of post-independence until now (Wulandari, Retno, & Purwoko, 2013, p. 3).

Based on the KPU's determination that the number of voters for the 2014 Presidential Election was 190.3 million and data from a quick count of two independent institutions, kawalpemilu.org or the UMM Infokom Institute, researchers took around 133 million voters, so the number of groups who did not vote reached 57 million because penetration was 24.89 percent (Mulya, 2014). The findings of Warring-Angin and Zainal's study (2018, p. 752) The findings of the investigation can be summarized as follows: (1) Children of the current age use social media extensively because it allows them to interact and communicate without having to openly display their personality traits. They also have no problems accessing the internet, so they can connect to networks with high intensity; (2) When networking on social media, they interact only with people they actually know in the real world, communication and interaction is carried out more intensively due to the limited time and place to interact due to the hectic daily activities that must be done every day, communication and interaction is carried out more intensively due to the limited time and place to interact due to the hectic daily activities that must be done every day However, they did not take advantage of the opportunity to interact face-to-face at the end of the week because they already feel comfortable interacting through social media, which does not require physical preparation; (3) Social media is also currently a source of reference for them for news and political information. If necessary, or if they believe they require extra information, they will pursue it through other means. The information gained will then be reviewed with family or friends before making a political decision; (4) Their political participation is relatively low since the participants do not fully get that the definition of politics encompasses many aspects of life. Politics was only identified with political parties and political actors by the participants. As a result, they have not participated actively in politics, both online and offline.

Zhang and Lin (2014) did another study on the influence of social media on political engagement in a study titled Political Participation in an Unexpected Place: How Individuals Engage in Politics through Social Networking Sites in China. The study was carried out by and was published in the International Journal of Communication. This study looks at how people participate in politics through Social Networking Sites (SNS) in China, where participation channels are limited and the flow of online material is censored. This study suggests, using the survey method, that social networking sites provide not only a new channel for citizens to express political concerns, but also a new platform for the state to preserve its legitimacy. According to the conclusions of this study, democratization or freedom of political involvement in Mainland China, particularly among students who utilize social media, may take longer than projected. (Viani, 2017, p. 4)

In general, students are Agents of Change, and certain members of the general public are thought to be geniuses who know everything, even politics. Long before the publication of data on the impact of social media on student political activity, academics inquired about how frequently students acquire political information via social media. On October 25, 2018, the researcher conducted initial interviews with seven students, two from the PJKR Study Program and five from the English Education STKIP Pasundan Cimahi Class of 2015, about the political participation that respondents will face in 2019, specifically the 2019 Presidential Election. The interviews were done using the Whatsapp platform and seven questions about the intensity of students in accessing political material presented on their social media, however some students are still hesitant to see political news. The replies ranged from disliking politics to believing that politics was only employed in PPKn courses and that politics was solely about competing for power and clouding the surrounding environment. But when asked if you have a dream candidate lined up for the 2019 election? Yes, according to their conscience, the respondents responded. From the results of first observations by conducting closed-door interviews, it can be seen that the 2015 STKIP Pasundan students show strong political knowledge. Therefore, the researcher will alter the research respondents to STKIP Pasundan Students Batch 2018.

The 2019 Indonesian Presidential Election is looming, and it is believed that students would be reluctant to exercise their constitutional right to vote in this election. Science and technology, notably the discipline of communication, have made print media no longer the primary way of delivering political messages. Political communication isn't just limited to print media; it includes phone, radio, television, newspapers/magazines/websites/social media/posters/banners/elections. Since social media has become the primary means through which people communicate, it has also become a powerful political tool (Ivony, 2017).

When it comes to user-generated content (UGC), social media is defined as "media that supports collaboration between users who develop content" (Mandiberg in Ratnamulyani & Maknai, 2018). Boyd also stated that social media is a collection of software that enables individuals and communities to connect, exchange, interact, and collaborate or play with each other. UGC, or user-generated content, is the power of social media, where the content is provided by users, rather than editors, as in mass media (Ratnamulyani & Maknai, 2018, p. 156).

Researchers plan to conduct a study entitled The Effect of Smartphone Communication Devices and Instagram Social-Media on Political Participation Levels Ahead of the 2019 Presidential Election (Student Study of STKIP Pasundan Cimahi Class of 2018) based on their initial observations, data, and facts about student political participation and social media.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Smartphone Concept

Patria in Rahayu (2017, p. 10) claims that the term "smartphone" is derived from the English words "smart" and "phone" (p. 10). When we say "smart phone," we mean "smart phone." A smartphone, on the other hand, is a mobile phone with computer-like features (personal computer). Mini computers disguised as mobile phones are possible thanks to these features. Operating systems, such as those found on the iPhone OS, Android, Windows Phone, and RIM Blackberry, allow smartphones to function.

According to Backer in Putra (2017, p. 2), a smartphone is a phone with advanced capabilities: it is a form of capability from a Wireless Mobile Device (WMD) that can function like a computer by providing features like a personal digital assistant (PDA), internet access, email, and global Positioning System (GPS). Smartphones, like ordinary phones, provide additional functionalities such as a camera, video player, and MP3 player. In other words, cellphones can be characterized as mini-computers with several capabilities that can be utilized at any time and place.

The smartphone, according to Williams & Sawyer in Rahayu (2017, p. 11), is a cell phone with an integrated CPU, memory, screen, and modem. Smartphone is a multimedia phone that combines the functionality of a PC and a handset to create a luxurious device with text messages, cameras, music players, videos, games, email access, digital tv, search engines for personal information management, GPS features, internet telephony services, and credit card phones. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, a smartphone is a mobile phone with advanced capabilities, sometimes including computer-like features.

It may be inferred that the smartphone is a system-integrated mobile phone that functions as a communication device. This smartphone is a multimedia device that incorporates computer functionality.

Instagram is a social media platform

"Media" has been defined so far, say Laughey and McQuail in Nasrullah (2017, p. 3), because it's a communication tool. According to Nasrullah, mass communication theories show that this concept of media tends to be closer to its mass character. There is a propensity for all existing definitions of "media" to refer to technology and the means it uses when it's stated. For example, newspapers are a type of printed media; whereas radio and television are examples of electronic media; and the internet represents online media or networks in general (Nasrullah, 2017, p. 3).

However, according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the term media is defined as a tool or a medium of communication such as newspapers and magazines as well as radio stations, television channels, posters, and banners. Communications are conveyed through the media, according to Cangara in Nasrullah (2017, p. 5). Human senses, such as the eyes and ears, are the primary means of conveying information in this scenario. The mind processes the sensory data to arrive at a reaction or attitude, which is subsequently manifested in action.

No matter what position you take on the media, Meyrowitz in Nasrullah says that the expression of the word "media" may be understood by looking at the communication process itself (2017, p. 3). Three things are required for communication: an object, an organ, and a medium. Eyes are the object and the eye is the organ when watching a television show. A picture or visual serves as a bridge between the television and the human eye. To use a simple example, the media can serve as a conduit for disseminating information that has been generated throughout the course of a conversation.

It is possible to evaluate the quality of the media based on a variety of factors. Print media, which shows that the media is made using a printing press, and electronic media are examples of technology-based criteria, according to Nasrullah (2017, p. 4). For example, audio-visual material that can be accessible via the senses of hearing and seeing are examples of sources or organs that can explain how to obtain or process message codes. As the message was disseminated, others wrote it down. There are many different types of broadcast media (broadcast), such as television stations, where the media is the core of message production, and the message can be experienced by everyone who has a television set. You can also categorize based on how the audience gets their material, for as through traditional or innovative forms of distribution.

This will make it easier for everyone to see the media, according to Nasrullah (2017, page 4). It is only in this division that the media are treated as simply auxiliary means of disseminating information. Yet the power of the media also contributes to the creation of meaning and culture behind the scenes. This understanding of the media's influence makes it clear that

the media no longer merely transmits information; it also provides context for that information. When Marshall McLuhan coined the statement "the medium is the message" half a century ago, it brought early understanding that the medium is a message that alters human communication patterns, communication culture, and even language.

Meyrowitz states in Nasrullah (2017, p. 4) that there are at least three expressions to comprehend how the media works. According to Meyrowitz, the three expressions are as follows: 1) The medium as a channel (the medium as a vessel/conduit). Pipes, like streams, are conveyances of water that follow predetermined grooves. The medium is the route via which the message is delivered, or in the case of the radio, the sound is the material delivered. 2) Medium is a type of language (medium as language). The language itself serves as the media. This means that the media contains something distinctive that can represent an expression or convey a message. 3) Medium as environment (medium as environment) The notion is that the media cannot be seen solely via the content, but must also be seen through the context. The researcher might characterize the medium from multiple angles after learning the three views suggested by Meyrowitz in observing it. Medium is defined not just by the technical or technological concerns it contains, whether in the form of print, audio, visual, analog digital, or other. The medium can then contain values that are not merely a way of communicating messages, but also have an impact on social, cultural, economic, and even political dimensions.

Although the core concepts of media and social have been explained, Burton in Nasrullah (2017, p. 8) contends that it is difficult to define social media solely on the basis of technological instruments. Before determining what is meant by social media, a method based on social theories is required to establish what distinguishes social media from other media on the internet. In addition, there is a need for particular conversations to investigate the link between the media and society.

According to Nasrullah (2017, p. 11), the following are some definitions of social media: 1) According to Mandiberg (2012), social media is a platform that promotes collaboration among content producers (user-generated content). 2) According to Shirky (2008), social media and social software are tools that boost users' ability to share, collaborate (to collaborate), among users, and take collective action, all of which are outside the framework. organizational and institutional. 3) According to Boyd (2009), social media is a collection of software that allows individuals and communities to congregate, share, interact, and in certain circumstances cooperate or play with one another. Social media has the power of user-generated content (UGC), which is created by users rather than editors, as in traditional mass media institutions. 4) According to Van Dijk (2013), social media is a media platform that focuses on the existence of users and makes it easier for them to undertake activities and collaborate. As a result, social media can be viewed as an online medium (facilitator) that develops user relationships as well as a social link. 5) According to Meike and Young (2012), social media is a convergence of personal communication in the sense of sharing between individuals (to be shared one on one) and public media in the sense of sharing with anyone without any individual specificity.

It is possible to conclude that social media is a location or means for users to engage in social activities such as sharing, collaborating and collaborating between users through the use of internet facilities and accessible to everyone without requiring specific persons to join.

Political Participation as a Concept

Political engagement, according to Budiardjo (2013, p. 367), is the activity of a person or group of people to actively participate in political life, such as choosing state leaders and, directly or indirectly, influencing government policies (public policy). These activities include things like voting in general elections, going to general meetings, contacting or lobbying government officials or members of parliament, joining a party or a social movement with direct action, and so on.

Also, Surbakti (2007, p. 140) says that "political participation is when ordinary citizens are involved in making all decisions that affect or affect their lives." So, this kind of participation is important for every ordinary citizen because it affects his life, not just for the good of the state or anyone who wants to help make policy decisions. So, now you know why it's important to take part in any field.

Politics is the action of bullies who want to influence government choices, according to Sastroatmodjo (1995, p.68). As a result, it is apparent who is involved, how the process works, and what the participation's goal is. The primary focus is on the people. Current events in government are being influenced by the process. Its goal is to have an impact on government policy.

Based on some of the opinions above, we know that political participation is the activity of citizens in different community structures, whether consciously or not, to influence political processes that help decide government policy. It is also clear that politics is closely related to the state, so the policies taken are also government policies.

Presidential Election in 2019

The 2019 Indonesian Presidential General Election is a democratic process for choosing the President and Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia for the years 2019-2024. Joko Widodo-Ma'ruf Amin received 55.50 percent of the votes in the general election, while Prabowo Subianto-Sandiaga Uno received 44.50 percent. This election takes place concurrently with the legislative general election.

The General Election Commission of the Republic of Indonesia officially released the results of this general election on Tuesday, May 21, 2019, in the morning. However, the Prabowo-Sandi National Winning Body refused to accept the results of this presidential election since they were deemed to be replete of unfairness, fraud, and arbitrariness. As a result, the Prabowo-Sandi BPN petitioned the Constitutional Court about the presidential election results.

METHOD

According to Komara (2011, p. 77), the scientific method is a procedure or series of methodical stages for acquiring scientific information or science. Science is the body of knowledge attained using the scientific process. A method is a procedure or strategy for determining something through systematic steps. This study employs a quantitative methodology.

The purpose of this research is to establish a causal link between variables. A causal relationship is a causative relationship according to Sugiyono's (2011, p. 62) perspective. As a result, there exist both independent and dependent variables (influenced). Students' use of smartphones, Instagram, and other social media, as well as their involvement in politics, are all part of the research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Pearson Moment Coefficient Product Test (PPM)

SPSS for Windows version 20 is used in this test. In the following manner, the test findings are summarized:

Table 1. PPM Correlation Coefficient Test Result

		Smartphone Communication Tool	Social Media Platform Instagram	Political Participation
Smartphone Communication Tool	Pearson Correlation	1	,556**	,394**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000	,000
	N	83	83	83
Social Media Platform Instagram	Pearson Correlation	,556**	1	,632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000		,000
	N	83	83	83
Political Participation	Pearson Correlation	,394**	,632**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	
	N	83	83	83

Correlation values for PPM variables X₁ (Smartphone Communication Tool) and X₂ (Social Media Platform Instagram) were found to be low and high, respectively, in Table 1.1, which indicates that the correlation coefficient for X₁ is low, while the correlation coefficient for X₂ was high. X₁ (Smartphone Communication Tool) and X₂ (Social Media Platform Instagram) both have significance values of 0.000. As a result, it may be argued that X₁ and X₂ are statistically significant in respect to Y, as their significance values are both less than or equal to 0.000.

Test for Determination Coefficient

SPSS for Windows version 20 is used in this test. In the following manner, the test findings are summarized:

Table 2 shows the results of determination tests

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,634 ^a	,402	,387	1,57832	,402	26,869	2	80	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Platform Instagram, Smartphone Communication Tool

Because of what is shown in Table 1.2, a reduction to 40.2% yields a R Square of 0.402% for the Determination Test of the variables X₁ and X₂. It's possible to say that a moderate decision has been made in regard to the variables.

Figure 1 Pie Chart showing the Influence of X₁ and X₂ on Y

Figure 1 depicts the percentage of Determination Test findings in the form of a pie chart demonstrating the influence of factors X₁ and X₂ on Y. The final number of 40.2 percent is driven by Smartphone Communication Devices and Instagram Social Media, while the remaining 60% is influenced by variables outside of the study. Other elements that shape or change political engagement, according to Wawan and Dewi (2010, p. 44), include as follows: 1) Firsthand Knowledge. What the individual has experienced and is experiencing will mold and influence the individual's evaluation of social stimuli, both positively and negatively. 2) The influence of other persons who are regarded as significant. Other people in the individual's environment are one of the social factors that influence the individual's attitude. 3) The Influence of Culture. The culture in which a person lives and is raised has a significant impact on the formation of that person's mindset. 4) The Media. Television, radio, newspapers, magazines, and other kinds of mass media have a significant impact on moulding public opinion and trust as a medium of communication. 5) Educational and Religious Institutions. Educational and religious institutions, as a system, have an impact on the formation of views. This is due to the fact that both serve as the foundation for knowledge and moral conceptions within the individual. 6) Emotional Aspect. Not all forms of attitude are driven by one's surroundings and personal experience; sometimes a form of attitude is an emotional statement that works as a channel of irritation or diversion in the form of an ego protection mechanism.

If two variables X₁ and X₂ have a relationship with variable Y, the Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient is provided. Meanwhile, to determine the importance of the correlation, the analysis findings are interpreted as follows: if it is close to 1, the relationship level is extremely strong, and if it is close to 0, the relationship level is very low. Based on the findings of Table 1. The correlation value of the PPM variable for X₁ (Smartphone Communication Tool) is 0.394, whereas it is 0.632 for X₂ (Social Media Platform Instagram), indicating that the level of correlation coefficient for X₁ is comparatively low and relatively strong for X₂. The X₁ variable (Smartphone Communication Tool) has a significance value of 0.000, whereas X₂ (Instagram Social-Media) has a significance value of 0.000. The significance value of X₁ is 0.000 and X₂ is 0.000 than 0.05, therefore it can be stated that there is a significant connection between X₁ and X₂ towards Y.

In order to find out how well the independent variable can explain the dependent variable, the R² test is used. The R² percentile range is 0 R² 1 for the percentage test. The following are the results of the evaluation: When R² is near to zero, the effect is lower. R² has a stronger influence when its value is near to 1. If the X₁ and X₂ variables are lowered by 40%, then the R Squared value is 0.402 as shown in Table 1.2, the results of the Determination Test on Y. It's possible to say that a moderate decision has been made in regard to the variables.

Based on the findings of data testing on the X₁ variable The Effect of Smartphone Communication Devices and the X₂ Social Media Platform Instagram variable, the X₁ variable has a significant influence on the Political Participation Level of STKIP Pasundan Cimahi Students for the 2018 batch of 40.2 percent, with the remaining 59.8 percent determined by other variables outside of this research. According to Rahman (2007, p. 286), the factors that influence political participation include "modernization, changes in social class structure, the influence of intellectuals and modern mass communication, conflicts between groups of political leaders, and widespread government involvement in social, economic, and cultural affairs." According to this, smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media are among the elements listed due to the influence of information/news dissemination in Instagram social media, which is accessed via smartphones.

The influence and function of the mainstream media, particularly new media, in different elements of modern society's social life is growing. Social media has grown in importance as an effective tool in the political communication process, particularly during election campaigns, when it can mediate politicians with their supporters, namely between communicators and communicants distantly and massively. As a result, communicators can conduct political communication with their followers or constituents using social media, specifically to construct or form public opinion while mobilizing large political support. Social media usage has also expanded political communication networks, political

relationships, and popular political participation in elections. This may be observed in the endeavor to use Instagram social media as a tool to speed the process of social transformation in developing nations, as well as in the use of Instagram social media accounts to carry out political campaigns, political news, and propaganda.

Initially, Instagram accounts tended to be tied to friendship concerns. However, it is now beginning to mention a lot about politics, government, or state authority. Similarly, from the 2018-2023 West Java gubernatorial election to the 2019-2024 Presidential General Election, the Instagram timeline or content is packed with political content. They are frequently found in these political accounts, ranging from accurate content and statistics to fake news or hoaxes. The news or information provided on Instagram social media about current national political topics is frequently factual and even fake news. This is because 2019 has been a "political year" in preparation for the 2019-2024 Presidential and Vice-Presidential Elections. The existence of news that coincides with the Instagram timeline can influence public involvement, particularly student selection of candidate pairs from both camps.

On the basis of this intensity, David F. Roft and Frank in H, I, A Rahman (2007) state the type of citizen engagement. A spectator's level of involvement is the lowest, a participant's is the middle, and an activist's level of involvement is the highest. A pyramid of political engagement will form if the intensity of community involvement in political activities is leveled. These groups, which do not participate in any political activity at all, fall at the bottom of the political involvement pyramid. Above the apolitical masses is a subset known as the observation class, which is comprised of people who go to political parties' conventions, listen in on their speeches, read the news, and even vote in elections. Observers are followed by the participant group, which is one level higher. Campaign officers, active party members, and interest groups in social projects are commonplace in this category. The activist group sits above the organizational hierarchy.

Increasing participation can be attributed to the use of smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media. It is possible to participate in politics if one has a basic understanding of the political process. Kenneth Newton and Jan W. Van Deth in Marijan (2010, p. 82) believe that "there are four theories to explain the power of mass media," and that the relationship between smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media and political awareness is as follows: First, Reinforcement Theory. This idea asserts that the impact of the media is negligible. Basically, all that the media does is reflect and reinforce prevailing social attitudes and viewpoints. The theory of agenda setting. According to this theory, the media is incapable of determining our thoughts. The media, on the other hand, is thought to be able and able to impact our thoughts. Theories of Priming and Framing According to priming theory, the media has the power to influence since they focus on a small number of topics, rather than a larger number of topics. In the meantime, framing theory states that the media is put up to affect readers, viewers, and listeners' interpretations of a topic in a certain way. Theory of Direct Effects People's attitudes and actions, particularly their political ones, are said to be influenced directly by the media. Rather than just reflecting reality, the media, according to this notion, exert influence on it by providing context and meaning to what is being reported.

"Voting behavior is the tendency of people's choices in general elections, as well as their background in making that choice," says Sofiah in Nuari & Yustisiana (2015, p. 5). People's decisions and actions are affected by numerous things, including the news and information they receive via social media accounts, as Cangara (2017, p. 5) explains. There are a variety of factors and backgrounds to consider when responding to news, information, and information related to the 2019 Presidential General Election described by the account in this social media, but these factors and backgrounds are not the only ones to consider when making a decision about which candidate to vote for in the 2019 Presidential General Election.

Mobile phone communication tools and Instagram social media can have an impact on the issue of political involvement. Students in the Pasundan STKIP environment may be influenced to participate in politics by the dissemination of election-related news and information via Instagram social media accounts, both factual and fake. There is a prevalent belief that young people are agents of change, and that some regular people are intellectuals who know everything, even politics. Students' political knowledge is predicted to grow as a result of news being disseminated via social media such as Instagram.

Politics participation and political awareness are intertwined. "Political engagement is intimately tied to political awareness," says Budiardjo (2013, p. 369), since those who are more conscious that they are being ruled desire the right to speak in government management. The results of the study of STKIP Pasundan Students Class of 2018 show, as described above, that smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media have an impact on growing student political participation simultaneously.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the F test, the condition of using smartphone communication tools and Instagram social media on political engagement in STKIP Pasundan Class 2018 students can be used to make a judgment on the X_1 and X_2 variables that simultaneously impact Y. Based on the results of data testing on the X_1 variable The Effect of Smartphone

Communication Devices and the X2 variable Social Media Instagram, 40.2% of the Political Participation Rate of STKIP Pasundan Cimahi Students for the 2018 batch is significantly influenced by these variables, while the remaining 59.8% is determined by variables outside the scope of this study.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Budiardjo, M. (2013). *Dasar-Dasar Ilmu Politik*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [2]. Fenyapwain, M. M. (2013). Pengaruh Iklan Politik Dalam Pemilukada Minahasa Terhadap Partisipasi Pemilih Pemula Di Desa Tounelet Kecamatan Kakas. *Journal "Acta Diurna"*, 1(1), 6-7.
- [3]. H. I, A. Rahman. (2007). *Sistem Politik Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- [4]. Ivony. (2017, 10 30). *10 Media Politik Secara Umum*. Retrieved 11 14, 2018, from PakarKomunikasi.com: <https://pakarkomunikasi.com/media-komunikasi-politik>
- [5]. Komara, E. (2011). *Filsafat Ilmu dan Metodologi Penelitian*. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
- [6]. Marijan, K. (2010). *Sistem Politik Indonesia Konsolidasi Demokrasi Pasca Orde Baru*. Jakarta: Kencana Predana Media Group.
- [7]. Mulya, R. (2014, Juli 21). *Aneh, Jumlah Golput Mencapai 57 Juta Suara?* Retrieved Oktober 21, 2018, from Republika: <https://www.republika.co.id/berita/pemilu/berita-pemilu/14/07/21/n919hn-aneh-jumlah-golput-mencapai-57-juta-suara>
- [8]. Nasrullah, R. (2017). *Media Sosial*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [9]. Nuari, R., & Yustisiana, B. (2015). Pengaruh Kampanye Capres-Cawapres di Media Sosial terhadap Partisipasi Pemilih Pemula pada Pemilihan Presiden 2014. *Jurnal FISIP UI*, 11-26.
- [10]. Perangin-angin, L. L., & Zainal, M. (2018). Partisipasi Politik Pemilih Pemula dalam Bingkai Jejaring Sosial di Media Sosial. *Jurnal Aspikom*, 3(4), 737-754.
- [11]. Putra, A., Susanti, C. D., Yusari, I., Silitonga, I., & Amrie, M. H. (2014). *Politik Pemilih Muda (Partisipasi Politik Anak Muda di Pekanbaru, Jakarta, Cirebon, Palu dan Jayapura)*. Jakarta: Perkumpulan Demos.
- [12]. Putra, D. A. (2017). Smart[phone Sebagai Gaya Hidup. *Jurnal FISIP USU*, 1-11.
- [13]. Rahayu, S. (2017). Pengaruh Penggunaan Smartphone Terhadap Pemenuhan Informasi Mahasiswa Prodi S1 Ilmu Perpustakaan Fakultas Adab dan Humaniora UIN Ar-Raniry Angkatan 2015. *Skripsi*. Banda Aceh: UIN Ar-Raniry.
- [14]. Rahmadani, S. (2017). Pengaruh Media Sosial Terhadap Partisipasi Memilih Masyarakat Sumatera Barat Pada Pilgub Sumbar Tahun 2015 (Penelitian Pada Followers dan Likers Irwan Prayitno Dalam Kampanye Pilgub Sumbar 2015). *Skripsi*. Padang: Universitas Andalas (Tidak Diterbitkan).
- [15]. Rahmanto. (2017). *Partisipasi Masyarakat Desa Tahun Talun Kecamatan Ngebel Kabupaten Ponorogo dalam Pemilihan Kepala Desa di Desa Talun Kecamatan Ngebel Kabupaten Ponorogo Provinsi Jawa Timur*. Ponorogo: Universitas Muhammadiyah Ponorogo.
- [16]. Ratnamulyani, I. A., & Maksud, B. I. (2018). Peran Media Sosial Dalam Peningkatan Partisipasi Pemilih Pemula. *Sosiohumaniora - Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Soisal dan Humaniora*, 154-161.
- [17]. Sastroatmodjo, S. (1995). *Perilaku Politik*. Semarang: IKIP Semarang Press.
- [18]. Sugiyono. (2011). *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi*. Bandung: ALFABETA.
- [19]. Surbakti, R. (2007). *Memahami Ilmu Politik*. Jakarta: Gramedia Widya Sarana Indonesia.
- [20]. Viani, A. N. (2017). Pengaruh Twitter Terhadap Tingkat Partisipasi Politik (Remaja dalam Pilkada Serentak 2015 pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Informatika Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta Angkatan 2014). *Skripsi*, (p. 4). Surakarta.
- [21]. Wulandari, H. S., Retno, N., & Purwoko. (2013). Hubungan Tingkat Sosial Ekonomi Terhadap Tingkat Partisipasi Politik Etnis Keturunan Tionghoa Dalam Pilwalkot Semarang 2010. *Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*.
- [22]. Wawan A, Dewi M.2010. Teori dan Pengukuran Pengetahuan, Sikap, dan Perilaku Manusia. Yogyakarta : Nuha Medika.
- [23]. Zhang, X., & Lin, W.-Y. (2014). Political Participation in an Unlikely Place: How Individuals Engage in Politics through Social Networking Sites in China. *International Journal of Communication*, 8, 21-42.